

Effect of different treatments at early postpartum period on uterine involution and subsequent reproductive performance in dairy cows

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to investigate the effectiveness of PGF₂ α and GnRH injections at early lactation on placental drop, uterine involution and subsequent reproductive performance in dairy cows. The study was conducted in El-Salhya dairy cattle breeding farm on 64 lactating dairy cows. Cows were assigned into the following groups: PGF₂ α treated group (18 cows), received PGF₂ α immediately after calving. GnRH treated group (17 cows), received GnRH analogue on 13-15 day postpartum (pp). PGF₂ α plus GnRH treated group (15 cows), received PGF₂ α immediately after calving and GnRH analogue on 13-15 day pp. Control group included 14 cows which were left without treatment. The reproductive tract of the cows was examined twice weekly by rectal palpation and transrectal ultrasound scanning to assess the postpartum uterine involution and the resumption of ovarian activity. Blood samples were obtained parallel with the reproductive examination for progesterone assay. Cows treated immediately after calving with PGF₂ α showed an earlier placental drop compared to the non treated ones. Cows treated immediately after calving with PGF₂ α showed an earlier uterine involution compared to those in the control and GnRH treated group. There was no significant difference in reproductive performance among control and treated groups. In conclusion, administration of PGF₂ α and GnRH during the early postpartum period did not significantly improve the reproductive performance; however, they slightly improve the time required for placental drop and uterine involution.

Key words: Dairy cows, PGF₂ α , GnRH, uterine involution, reproductive performance parameters.

Introduction

Reproductive performance in dairy cows is a key factor affecting profitability of the dairy industry (Galvão et al., 2013). The increased genetic capability of cows for milk production is accompanied by substantial reduction in reproductive efficiency (Shrestha et al., 2005). Poor fertility has been the single most important factor for culling dairy cattle causing huge economic losses (Rajala-

Schultz and Grohn, 1999). The optimal calving interval is generally considered to be about 12 months for the maximum economic benefit, this means that cows should conceive in about three months after the last calving (Sørensen and Østergaard, 2003). To achieve this, a normal uterine involution, an early onset of estrus cycle with resumption of ovarian cyclicity postpartum, a high estrus detection rate and a high

conception rate are required (Hussein et al., 1992). In that sense, management practices that hasten uterine involution during the early postpartum period and early resumption of postpartum ovarian cyclicity within 60 days postpartum or before are expected to improve reproductive performance (Cerri et al., 2004). Normal uterine involution plays a key role in the future reproduction of the dairy cattle (Bell and Roberts, 2007). The timing of uterine involution coincides with the recovery of complete fertility in postpartum cows. Thus, most investigators consider uterine involution as the initial step to reestablishment of normal fertility (Lucy, 2003). Postpartum administration of prostaglandin F₂ α enhance uterine contractility and lochial clearing from the uterus after calving so it hasten uterine involution and initiate earlier postpartum cyclicity which improved the reproductive performance (Nanda et al., 2003).

Therefore, the main objective of the present study was to investigate the effectiveness of PGF₂ α and GnRH injection at early lactation on placental drop, uterine involution and subsequent reproductive performance parameters in dairy cows.

Materials and methods

Animal

This study was conducted in El-Salhya dairy cattle on 64 lactating dairy cows during the period from October 2011 to January 2013. The parity of the cows ranged from 2 to 5, they were housed freely in a semi-shed yards. They were

fed a total mixed ration. Cows were machine milked three times daily, and the average 305-day milk yield was 7500-8500 kg.

Experimental design and reproductive examinations

Cows were randomly assigned into the following groups: (i) First group (PGF₂ α treatment group, n=18 cows), each one received 625 μ g of synthetic PGF₂ α (Estrumate®, Schering-Plough Animal Health) immediately after calving. (ii) Second group (GnRH treatment group, n=17 cows), each cow received 20 μ g of GnRH analogue (Receptal®, Intervet, Holland) on day 13-15 postpartum. (iii) Third group (PGF₂ α plus GnRH treatment group, n=15 cows), each one received 625 μ g Cloprostenol immediately after calving and 20 μ g Buserelin on day 13-15 postpartum. (iv) Fourth group included 14 control cows which were left without treatment. Four cows in the control group and one cow in GnRH treatment group were culled and their data were excluded from the statistical analysis of the uterine involution and subsequent reproductive performance parameters.

The reproductive tract of the cows was examined twice weekly per rectal palpation starting from the 1st week after calving till day 55 \pm 5 postpartum, or until AI to assess the postpartum uterine involution and the resumption of ovarian activity. The uterine involution was assessed according to Stephen (2010). Transrectal ultrasound scanning (Honda HS-1500 V, Aichi, Japan) of the ovaries was performed twice weekly starting from day 11 \pm 1.0 till the end of the study to assess the resumption of postpartum ovarian activity.

ELISA for progesterone assay in blood

Blood samples were collected twice weekly from day 11±1 postpartum until day 55±5, or until AI for progesterone assay. The blood was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to separate the serum. Then serum was transferred into a labeled eppendorf tubes and stored at -20 °C until analysis. The progesterone assay was carried out according to Check et al. (1995) using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay technique in an ELISA reader (State Fax 4200, USA). Cows with serum P₄ concentrations ≥ 1ng/mL on at least two consecutive blood samplings were considered to have luteal activity (Stevenson, 1997). Ovulation was considered to have occurred 5 days before the first rise day of luteal activity (Shrestha et al., 2005).

Subsequent reproductive performance parameters

Cows were followed up after treatment and all the reproductive parameters were obtained as 1st postpartum ovulation, resumption of luteal activity (based on blood progesterone), interval from calving to first observed heat, interval from calving to first service, number of services/ conception, first service conception rate, calving to conception interval and conception rate.

Statistical analysis

The obtained results were statistically analyzed using statistical analysis by the GraphPad prism® version 5.01, GraphPad software, San Diego, CA, USA

Results

Placental drop

Cows treated immediately after calving with PGF2α showed an earlier placental

drop (8.3 ± 0.5 hours) compared to the non treated ones (9.3 ± 0.6 hours) however, the difference between them was non significant (Table, 1).

Table (1): Time required for placental drop in PGF2α treated cows and non-treated ones (mean ± S.E.)

Treated groups	n	Time of placental drop (hours)	Cows with retained placenta	
			n	%
PGF2α treated cows*	33	8.3 ± 0.5	3	9.1
Non treated cows †	31	9.3 ± 0.6	3	9.7

* Included cows in PGF2α treatment group (n=18) and those in PGF2α plus GnRH treatment group (n=15). †: Included cows in control group (n=14) and those in GnRH treatment group (n=17)

Uterine involution

The mean time required for uterine involution was 20.7 ± 0.49 days pp in control group while in PGF2α, GnRH and PGF2α plus GnRH, it was 19.4 ± 0.46, 20.3 ±0.62 and 19.4 ±0.50 days postpartum respectively. Cows treated immediately after calving with PGF2α irrespective of their group showed an earlier uterine involution compared to those in the control and GnRH treated group (Table, 2).

Table (2): Time required for uterine involution in control and treated groups (mean ± S.E.)

Treatment groups	n	Mean ± S.E. (Time / day)
PGF2α	18	19.4 ±0.46
GnRH	16	20.3 ±0.62
PGF2α plus GnRH	15	19.4 ±0.50
Control	10	20.7 ± 0.49

Subsequent reproductive performance parameters

All data concerning the reproductive performance parameters of the studied cows including 1st postpartum ovulation,

resumption of luteal activity, interval from calving to first observed heat, interval from calving to first service, number of services/ conception, first service conception rate, calving to

conception interval and conception rate are presented in Table (3). There were no significant differences in the fertility traits among control and treated groups

Table (3): Reproductive parameters among control and treatment groups (Mean \pm S.E.)

Groups	Interval to 1st P.P. ovulation* (days)	Interval to resumption of P.P. luteal activity* (days)	Interval from calving to 1st observed heat (days)	Interval from calving to 1st service (days)	No. of services / conception	1st service conception rate (%)	Calving to conception interval (days)	Conception rate %
PGF2 α	22.6 \pm 4.3	27.6 \pm 4.3	47.3 \pm 5.8	60.94 \pm 2.9	2.471 \pm 0.3	11.76	110.3 \pm 6.8	94%
GnRH	19.6 \pm 3.6	24.6 \pm 3.6	50.29 \pm 6.5	73.29 \pm 5.1	2.231 \pm 0.2	15.4	111 \pm 8.2	100%
PGF2 α plus GnRH	18 \pm 4.4	23 \pm 4.4	44.93 \pm 7.5	60.86 \pm 5.2	2.154 \pm 0.3	23.07	103.7 \pm 10	92.3%
Control	20.3 \pm 6.1	25.3 \pm 6.1	49.5 \pm 5.1	67.08 \pm 3.5	2.455 \pm 0.3	9.09	119.6 \pm 10	100%
P value	N.S (0.9034)	N.S (0.9034)	N.S (0.5137)	N.S (0.1216)	N.S (0.3146)		N.S (0.6749)	

*Based on blood progesterone profiles.

Discussion

The present study revealed that the time required for placental drop was numerically shorter in cows given PGF2 α immediately after calving than those in the non treated cows. These results were in agreement with the studies of Lindell and Kindahl (1983); Herschler and Lawrence (1984) and El-Azab et al. (1988) who found that PGF2 α administration at calving shorten the time required for placental expulsion. When exogenous uterotonic products were administered (oxytocin or prostaglandins), the myometrium responded with strong contractions (Gajewski et al., 1999). These contractions are one of the factors involved in the separation of cotyledonary villi from the

maternal caruncular crypts resulting in the detachment of the fetal membranes (Sheldon et al., 2008). On the other hand, the present study disagreed with the data of Hopkins (1983); Eiler et al. (1984) and Fattouh et al. (1986) who reported that there was no association between PGF2 α injection at parturition and the time of placental drop or uterine involution in cows or buffaloes.

The present study revealed that the time required for uterine involution was numerically shorter in the groups given PGF2 α and PGF2 α plus GnRH treatment groups, than those in the control and GnRH treated groups, respectively. These results were in agreement with the studies of Odensvik (1995); Randel et al. (1996); Gajewski et al.

(1999) and Melendez et al. (2004) who found an association between PGF₂ α injection in the early postpartum period and the acceleration of uterine involution. On the other hand, the present study disagreed with the studies of Hopkins (1983); Eiler et al. (1984) and Fattouh et al. (1986) who reported that there was no association between PGF₂ α injection at parturition and the time of uterine involution in cows or buffaloes. In that sense, results of Hendricks et al. (2006) and Stephen (2010) showed that treatment with PGF₂ α in early postpartum period did not result in any beneficial effect on the time to gross uterine involution compared to untreated control.

In the present study, there were no significant differences among the control and the treated groups concerning the interval from calving to first observed heat, interval from calving to first service, number of services/conception, first service conception rate and calving to conception interval. However, cows in PGF₂ α +GnRH treated group showed an improvement in the reproductive performance parameters than those in control and other treated groups. These results are in agreement with the studies of Hopkins (1983); Prakash and Madan (1986); Hendricks et al. (2006) and Stephen (2010) who found that injection of PGF₂ α did not result in any beneficial effect on the fertility parameters. In association with the present study, several reports demonstrated no effect on breeding performance after early postpartum

administration of GnRH (Padula and Macmillan, 2002; Tucker et al., 2011). On the other hand, the present study disagreed with the studies of McClary et al. (1989) and Melendez et al. (2004) who found that injection of PGF₂ α in the early postpartum was associated with higher fertility. Moreover, Nash et al. (1980); Benmrاد and Stevenson (1986) and Jeong et al. (2012) found that administration of GnRH during early postpartum period improved subsequent reproductive performance in dairy cow. In conclusion, the present study revealed that administration of PGF₂ α and GnRH during the early postpartum period did not significantly improve the reproductive performance. However, they slightly improve the time required for placental drop and uterine involution.

References

- Bell, M.J. and Roberts, D.J. (2007):** The impact of uterine infection on dairy cow's performance. *Theriogenology*, 68: 1074-1079.
- Benmrاد, M. and Stevenson, J. (1986):** Gonadotropin-releasing hormone and prostaglandin F₂ α for postpartum dairy cows: estrous, ovulation, and fertility traits. *J. Dairy Sci.*, 69: 800-811.
- Cerri, R. L. A.; Santos, J. E. P.; Juchem, S. O.; Galvao, K. N. and Chebel, R. C. (2004):** Timed artificial insemination with estradiol cypionate or insemination at estrus in high-producing dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sci.*, 87(11): 3704-3715.
- Check, J. H.; Ubelacker, L. and Lauer, C. C. (1995):** Falsely elevated steroidal assay levels related to heterophile antibodies against various animal species. *Gynecologic and obstetric investigation*, 40(2): 139-140.

- Eiler, H.; Hopkins, F.M.; Armstrong-Backus, C.S. and Lyke, W.A. (1984):** Uterotonic effect of prostaglandin F₂ alpha and oxytocin on the postpartum cow. *Am. J. Vet. Res.*, 45(5):1011-1014.
- El-Azab, E.A.; El-Azab, M.A.; Sharawy, S.M. and Labib, F.M. (1988):** Evaluation of various uterotonic single treatments for prophylaxis of retained placenta in dairy cows. *Assiut Vet. Med. J.* 19 (38): 165-172.
- Fattouh, S. M.; Whitmore, H.; Lodge, J. R. and Gustafsson, B. (1986):** Effects of cloprostenol on uterine involution and first postpartum ovulation in Holstein cows. *Assiut. Vet. Med. J.*, 16: 32.
- Gajewski, Z.; Thun, R.; Faundez, R. and Boryezko, Z. (1999):** Uterine motility in the cow during puerperium. *Reprod. Domest. Anim.*, 34: 185–191.
- Galvão, K. N.; Federico, P.; De Vries, A. and Schuenemann, G. M. (2013):** Economic comparison of reproductive programs for dairy herds using estrus detection, timed artificial insemination, or a combination. *J. Dairy Sci.*, 96:2681-2693.
- Hendricks, K.E.M.; Bartolome, J.A.; Melendez, P.; Risco, C. and Archbald, L.F. (2006):** Effect of repeated administration of PGF₂alpha in the early postpartum period on the prevalence of clinical endometritis and probability of pregnancy at first insemination in lactating dairy cows. *Theriogenology*, 65(8): 1454-1464.
- Herschler, R. C. and Lawrence, J. R. (1984):** A prostaglandin analogue for therapy of retained placenta. *Veterinary Medicine and Small animals Clinician*, 79: 822- 826.
- Hopkins, F. M. (1983):** Prostaglandins and the postpartum bovine society for proc. Ann. Meeting. Soc. for Theriog., pp. 124-128.
- Hussein, F. M.; Eilts, B.E.; Paccamonti, D.L. and Younis, M.Y.(1992):** Effect of repeated injections of GnRH on reproductive parameters in postpartum anestrous dairy cows. *Theriogenology*, 37: 605-617.
- Jeong, J. K.; Kang, H. G. Hur, T. Y. and Kim, I. H. (2012):** The administration of gonadotropin-releasing hormone around the first postpartum month increases subsequent reproductive performance in dairy cows. *Reproduction, Fertility and Development*, 25(1): 154-155.
- Lindell, J. O. and Kindahl, H. (1983):** Exogenous prostaglandin F₂ alpha promotes uterine involution in the cow. *Acta. Vet. Scand.*, 24: 269–274.
- Lucy, M.C. (2003):** Physiological mechanisms leading to reproductive decline in dairy cattle. En: *Reproductive loss in dairy cows: Is the trend reversible?*. St. Paul, Minnesota, USA; Proceedings of the II Bi-Annual W.E. Petersen Symposium.
- McClary, D. G.; Putnam, M.R.; Wright, J. C. and Sartin, J. L. (1989):** Effect of early postpartum treatment with prostaglandin F₂α on subsequent fertility in the dairy cows. *Theriogenology*, 31 (3) : 565-570.
- Melendez, P.; McHale, J.; Bartolome, J.; Archbald, L.F. and Donovan, G.A. (2004):** Uterine involution and fertility of Holstein cows subsequent to early postpartum PGF₂α treatment for acute puerperal metritis. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 87 (10): 3238–3246.
- Nanda, A. S.; Barr, P. S. and Prabhakar, S. (2003):** Enhancing the reproductive performance in dairy buffaloes: major constrains and achievement. *Reprod. Suppl.*, 61: 27–36.
- Nash, J.G.; Ball, L. and Olson, J.D. (1980):** Effects on reproductive performance of administration of GnRH to early postpartum dairy cows. *J. Anim. Sci.*, 50:1017–1021.
- Odensvik, K. (1995):** The use of flunixin for regulation of the prostaglandin biosynthesis especially in the bovine species. Ph.D.Vet. Thesis. Swedish Univ. Agri. Sci., Suppsala, Sweden.
- Padula, A. M. and Macmillan, K. L. (2002):** Reproductive responses of early postpartum dairy cattle to continuous treatment with a GnRH agonist (deslorelin)

for 28 days to delay the resumption of ovulation. *Anim. Reprod. Sci.*, 70:23-36.

Prakash, B.S. and Madan, M. L. (1986): Retained placenta and prostaglandin F_{2α} profile after induced parturition in karan swiss cattle. *Brit. Vet. J.*, 142: 210-217.

Rajala-Schultz, P.J. and Grohn, Y.T. (1999): Culling of dairy cows. Part III. Effects of diseases, pregnancy status and milk yield on culling in Finnish Ayrshire cows. *Prevent Vet Med*, 41:295–309.

Randel , R. O .; Lammoglia , M.A .; Lewis , A.W.; Neuendroff, D.A and Guthrie , M. J. (1996) : Exogenous PGF_{2α} enhanced Gn-RH induced LH release in postpartum cows. *Theriogenology*, 45: 643.

Sheldon, I.M.; Williams, E.J.; Miller, A.N.A. Nash, D.M. and Herath, S. (2008): Uterine diseases in cattle after parturition. *Vet. J.*, 176:115–121.

Shrestha, HK.; Nakao, T.; Suzuki, T.; Akita, M. and Higaki, T. (2005): Relationships between body condition score, body weight, and some nutritional parameters in plasma and resumption of

ovarian cyclicity postpartum during pre-service period in high-producing dairy cows in a subtropical region in Japan. *Theriogenology*, 64:855–866.

Sørensen, J.T. and Østergaard, S. (2003): Economic consequences of postponed first insemination of cows in a dairy cattle herd. *Livestock Production Science*, 79: 145-153.

Stephen, C.P. (2010): Effect of ecbolic therapy on uterine involution, disease /and reproductive performance in dairy cows. Thesis university of Guelph, Canada. :72-83.

Stevenson, J.S. (1997): Clinical reproductive physiology of the cow. In: Youngquist, R.S. (ed), *Current Therapy in Large Animal Theriogenology*, Philadelphia: W B Saunders, P. 258.

Tucker, A. L.; Sanchez, H. L.; Tucker, W. B.; Williams, A. and Fuquay, J. W. (2011): Effects of Early Postpartum GnRH and Prostaglandin F_{2α} Administration on Reproductive Activity and Ovulation Synchronization in Lactating Dairy Cows. *Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 10(7): 900-908.